

HEALTH INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Background

Organization and Business Domain

Health information is very critical information for a person because it affects to healthy life of a person. The context of health information management is not limited to one organization. It spreads through all over the society in terms of hospitals, clinical centers, and many more health organizations. So, this system can cater all these organizations and not just one organization. As well as individuals who are interested in maintaining health-related data in a central database, they can use this system.

Overview of the Existing System

Today, there are many institutes which includes government hospitals, private hospitals, channeling centers and clinics to get medicine, to check-up the body and to do all the other activities related to health. People within the society use this all institutes when there is a health problem. One person may go to hospital to get the medicine and same person to check-up his body may go to another private channeling center. As so, time to time they use these different institutes when a health problem arises. They do not maintain any record for their health-related information. They just go and get the service from any institution when the requirement arises.

Problem of this situation is, since the health information is very critical because it decide the life of a person, there is a need to maintain health information in a central location where person can get his/her past records related to health. As a patient this information are more important and as a doctor patient's past health records are very much important when diagnosing the disease of a patient.

The main problems of the existing systems are,

- Health information are maintained by one party.
- Existing systems are only for a one health institute.
- Most of the government hospital still use paper-based recordings.

System Analysis

Through this project our aim was to develop a web-based application to maintain health information in a central database. When there is a central health information management system for patients, it leads to accurate health decisions. The System will be used by the individuals who have intent to maintain their health database by themselves and will have the access after creating their user profile. The main functions this system will serve are as follows.

Register individuals and doctors

Individuals can create their own accounts to access this system. Also, they can maintain profile information, can delete, edit, and update that information as needed. Doctors can register by giving their information and by checking that information, authenticating officer will approve the registration. After that doctors can login to the system.

Manage health information

Individuals can maintain their health-related information in this system. Prescription details, medical report details, blood pressure details, BMI values and sugar levels are the main types of data which can be maintained using this system.

Maintain checkup details

Patient meet up the doctor for medical consultation. At that moment doctor can view patient's personal information, medical history, medical reports and can add/update health related information which include drugs and

reports. And there are two ways to enter the details related to health when a patient goes to get medicine from a doctor.

- Patient can himself add prescription either by typing or uploading an image of a prescription if doctor refuses to use the system.
- If a doctor uses this system, doctor himself can add the prescription details to the patient's profile by logging to the system.

Generate and view reports

This system itself provides reports regarding health-related data and both individual and doctor can view these reports when and as needed.

System Development

MySQL (in WAMP Server) is used as the database management system. To develop the interface, we have used JavaScript, PHP, CSS and HTML. The coding done in VS Code IDE. Bootstrap was widely used throughout the designing of the template for the system. Two APIs used to create social logins and to get verification codes namely Google Sign-In and Textit.biz SMS Gateway respectively.

Conclusion

Health Information Management System is providing a platform to store health-related data and analyzes those data to take decisions by both persons and doctors. The main function of this system is maintaining a person's health-related data to take decisions regarding his/her health. The system contains two main modules namely person module and doctor module along with an authenticating officer module by looking at the user's perspective. This Health Information Management System (web-based system) namely MyHIMS is a system for storing a person's health related data in a one system or one place (Central Database).

References

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